

Gamified flipped classroom in education: a systematic review

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, gamified flipped classrooms (GFC) are a cutting-edge teaching method. Using gamification techniques with flipped classrooms (FC) significantly positively affects teachers and students. This study reviews the impact of GFC research on education methodically. Hence, the study investigated a comprehensive literature review of 52 empirical research publications published between 2018 and 2022 in various electronic databases and on the web. Note that the review established the foundation for the significance of upcoming research projects by critically assessing and evaluating the different inconsistencies in the literature. In addition to examining the contradictory results of previous research, the study offer a framework as well as guidance for future researchers in terms of theoretical models, methodology, game tools or online platforms, game activity, game elements, variables, and the impact of a GFC.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The educational landscape is continually evolving in line with the nation's brisk economic growth and development following the advancement of technology. Therefore, the curriculum for excellent education is designed to create a highly educated society capable of overcoming the challenges of modern living. Education is not only changing due to the technological environment but also due to the emergence of new methodologies [1]. The new approach emphasizes student-centered learning to enhance interaction and foster students' creativity and divergent thought. Here, game-based learning (GBL) refers to a teaching method that aids in boosting student engagement, and research on it has advanced over the past ten years.

According to Charlo *et al.* [1], gamification in education has been a quickly growing subject of study since 2013. Additionally, the 2019 e-learning trend report globally by Docebo demonstrates how gamification techniques in the classroom foster a favorable interaction between learning and teaching. The gamified flipped classrooms (GFC) strategy is among the most popular instructional innovations instructors implement worldwide [2]. Other than that, gamification works well to boost student engagement. The gamification of the flipped classrooms (FC) has been implemented to help instructors draw in students [3].

Bergmann and Sams [4] developed the FC teaching strategy to deal with the issue of students missing class. As an alternative to traditional classroom instruction, FC engages students in various learning activities, including independent online or digital learning outside class and task completion. Moreover, FC is a class taught the opposite way it would normally be [5]. Face-to-face instruction was previously used in the classroom, and individual or homework training was replaced with self-learning in the student's own space with multimedia materials available in advance. Meanwhile, gamification resembles the application of game design features for non-game contexts. Note that it is an approach that enhances rather than replaces teaching [5]. Figure 1 illustrates the difference between traditional learning and flipped classroom learning.

Figure 1. The difference between traditional learning and FC [6]

Nevertheless, the findings of research conducted by Lo and Hew [7] on the cognitive engagement accomplishment with regard to grade 9 students in Hong Kong cannot conclude that GFC learning is better than classrooms that are not gamified. They recommend conducting more research to examine the learning differences when employing the FC technique with GFC. Studies on gamification, specifically in the higher education context, still require a theoretical foundation and adequate design and measurement [5]. Although the data meta-analysis indicates that gamification favors learning and motivation, gamification research is still required to understand its benefits fully. Note that most studies focus on methodological assertiveness, gamification theory application, as well as analysis and assessment pertaining to learning processes, particularly in the setting of higher education [8].

A systematic review with respect to articles published between 2018 and 2022 in Scopus, Science Direct, ERIC, ProQuest, Dimensions, and Google Scholar was conducted using thematic and content analysis. These reviews offer insights into a GFC's trends, research techniques, and effects. In addition, the analysis will address the research questions outlined, namely: i) What theoretical models have been employed in a GFC?; ii) What methodologies were used in a GFC?; iii) What gaming tools or online platforms have been used in a GFC?; iv) What game activities and elements have been used in a GFC?; v) What variables have been explored; and vi) How does gamification in FCs impact students' learning?

2. RESESEARCH METHOD

There have been several recent studies on systematic assessments conducted worldwide. However, only a few educational research were conducted in the context of the GFC overview. The necessity for a systemic investigation of the effects of GFC in education is covered in this section. The preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses (PRISMA) approach, a published guideline for performing a systematic literature review (SLR), is employed in this analysis. Subsequently, the four essential sub-sections, comprising identification, screening, eligibility, as well as data abstraction, are also summarized in this section.

2.1. Identification

The systematic review process is broken down into three primary stages that helped choose various relevant papers for this study. The initial phase is keyword recognition and searching for connected, related terms using the thesaurus, dictionaries, encyclopedias, and prior research. As a result, search strings have been developed for the databases Scopus, Science Direct, ERIC, ProQuest, Dimensions, and Google Scholar after all pertinent terms had been chosen, as presented in Table 1. Total 144 papers were successfully retrieved from both databases as part of the current study endeavor's first stage with regard to the systematic review process.

Table 1. The search strings

Database	Keyword
Scopus	TITLE-ABS-KEY (game OR gamifi*) AND (flip OR "Flipped-classroom" OR "flipped classroom") AND (learning OR instruction OR education) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBSTAGE, "final")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2022) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2018)) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE, "English"))
Science Direct	"gamified" "gamification" "flipped classroom"
ERIC	(gamified OR gamification) AND flipped classroom
ProQuest	"Gamified flipped classroom"
Dimensions	"Gamified flipped classroom", "gamified" "gamification", "flipped classroom"
Google Scholar	"Gamified flipped classroom" OR "gamified" "gamification" OR "gamifying" AND "flipped classroom"

2.2. Screening

The second step refers to the data screening process, in which survey title, accessibility, overlap, year of publication, and unrelated articles were published. Based on what the researchers read in the abstract, only 103 similar publications were established after this approach was established. Table 2 lists the selection criteria for the lookup of pertinent data. The publication year ranges from 2018 to 2022, as well as only article journals are included. Note that the articles are only chosen in English.

Table 2. The selection criterion for searching

Criterion	Inclusion	Exclusion
Language	English	Non-English
Year	2022	<2022
Literature type	Journal (research articles only)	Journal (conference proceeding, book chapter)

2.3. Eligibility

The third step, called eligibility, has 59 items. At this point, all article titles and important content were carefully examined to ensure they met the inclusion criteria and complemented the present research's objectives. Four studies were excluded since they were irrelevant to the GFC. Hence, 52 papers are available for review Figure 2.

2.4. Data extraction and analysis

Further analysis of the 52 papers was conducted to present compiled data findings for the study topics. It is crucial to provide the data gleaned from the studies' validity and credibility. Consequently, a triangulation procedure was employed. First, a thorough examination and analysis of the ideas, methodology, goals, outcomes, and linkages between gamified studies and education will be conducted. All studies' information was collected while maintaining the validity of the research through a systematic keyword search. Finally, we finalized our triangulation process by conducting a document analysis to ensure our findings' convergence and verification. The following significant details were taken from each article: i) learning theories/models; ii) methods; iii) game activity; iv) gamification tools/platform; v) game elements; vi) variable; vii) findings. The flow diagram of the four stages involved in the systematic review process using the PRISMA statement is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Flow diagram of the proposed search study [9]

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on five suggested research questions, the study's results will be discussed in this part. The significant findings are presented in this section regarding the main research goals. To view the major issue discussed and analyzed, we extracted the top three keywords from the 52 papers. Correspondingly, the top three search terms were "gamified," "gamification," and "flipped classroom". Table 3 demonstrates the research article based on year and title. A study conducted between 2018 and 2022 discovered 52 articles about GFC strategies used in multi-level education. As a result, research on GFC has been published more frequently each year. Subsequently, the number of publications published annually is presented in Figure 3.

Table 3. The research article finding based on year

No	Author	Year	No	Author	Year
1	[3]	2020	27	[32]	2020
2	[5]	2021	28	[33]	2021
3	[6]	2020	29	[34]	2021
4	[7]	2020	30	[35]	2021
5	[10]	2020	31	[36]	2021
6	[11]	2020	32	[37]	2022
7	[12]	2022	33	[38]	2021
8	[13]	2021	34	[39]	2021
9	[14]	2019	35	[40]	2021
10	[15]	2018	36	[41]	2021
11	[16]	2019	37	[42]	2021
12	[17]	2018	38	[43]	2021
13	[18]	2018	39	[44]	2021
14	[19]	2020	40	[45]	2021
15	[20]	2020	41	[46]	2022
16	[21]	2019	42	[47]	2022
17	[22]	2021	43	[48]	2022
18	[23]	2019	44	[49]	2019
19	[24]	2019	45	[50]	2020
20	[25]	2020	46	[51]	2018
21	[26]	2021	47	[52]	2022
22	[27]	2018	48	[53]	2022
23	[28]	2018	49	[54]	2022
24	[29]	2019	50	[55]	2022
25	[30]	2020	51	[56]	2022
26	[31]	2020	52	[57]	2019

Figure 3. Number of publications each year

3.1. Theoretical models

In the 52 papers that were reviewed, more than half of the researchers applied the self-determination theory (SDT) to examine how gamification impacted student motivation by 43%, followed by the ARCS model by 11%, flow theory by 7%, cognitive learning theory, behavioral reinforcement theory, social comparison theory 5% each. Other theories by 9% include active learning theory, constructivism theory, sociocultural learning theory, taxonomy bloom, and trait activation theory (TAT). Note that learner and pedagogical models are among the additional models employed in the research of the GFC of 7%. Figure 4 shows the theories and model use in GFC studies.

Figure 4. Theory and model use in GFC studies

3.2. Methodology approach

The quantitative methodology was discovered to be applied by most studies, followed by the mixed-method approach. Meanwhile, the quantitative method was utilized in 32 studies using various data collection techniques, including experimental tests, assessments, and questionnaire surveys as shown in Figure 5. An analysis of the publications reveals that only one study employed a qualitative method and that 19 employed mixed-method to collect data utilizing various methodologies. Observations, surveys, interviews, and assessments are a few of these.

Figure 5. Method used in gamification studies

3.3. Gaming tools or online platform

The survey’s findings revealed that different platforms and tools were used to conduct teaching and learning activities through GFC. The platforms used in GFC are listed in Table 4. Nevertheless, some studies miss specifying the platforms and technologies employed for teaching and learning.

Table 4. Gaming tools or online platforms used in GFC

No	Author	Year	Tools/Platform
1	[3]	2020	Ed puzzle, Kahoot! Nearpod, Socrative, Quizlet, and Padlet
2	[5]	2021	Kahoot! Quizalize and Quizizz
3	[6]	2020	ioEduc and Kahoot!
4	[7]	2020	Learning management system (Moodle)
5	[10]	2020	Gamified learning course
6	[11]	2020	LMS (Moodle) and YouTube
7	[12]	2022	Kahoot or Socrative, or CrossQuestion educational game.
8	[13]	2021	Edmodo App
9	[14]	2019	Educaplay
10	[15]	2018	YouTube, Moodle, Kahoot!
11	[16]	2019	The iSpring Quiz Maker
12	[17]	2018	The Protégé designed by Playware Studios
13	[18]	2018	Moodle
14	[19]	2020	Socrative
15	[20]	2020	Gymkhana room for education and evaluation in nursing studies (GREENS©)
16	[21]	2019	Socrative
17	[22]	2021	The online University platform, Moodle
18	[23]	2019	Kahoot!
19	[24]	2019	Taboo™ or Time's up!™, Kahoot™, Socrative™, Quizizz™, Collaborative Problems Jigsaw
20	[25]	2020	Socrative and Kahoot
21	[26]	2021	Socrative, Kahoot, Moodle and Blackboard Collaborate.
22	[27]	2018	Moodle
23	[28]	2018	Cisco and Secure Volunteer
24	[29]	2019	Unity3d video game engine
25	[30]	2020	Game immersion questionnaire (GIQ)
26	[31]	2020	Jigsaw, Kahoot, Socrative
27	[32]	2020	TipOn
28	[33]	2021	Kahoot! Quizlet, and Prodigy
29	[34]	2021	Self-develop gamification project
30	[35]	2021	Computer-assisted games
31	[36]	2021	AI-enabled gamified web-based online learning application
32	[37]	2022	Kahoot!
33	[38]	2021	Gamified interactive e-book
34	[39]	2021	Self-develop gamification learning
35	[40]	2021	Econplus champions league and Kahoot!
36	[41]	2021	Vocabulary games from Khate-Sefied
37	[42]	2021	Kahoot!
38	[43]	2021	Moodle
39	[44]	2021	Zoom
40	[45]	2021	CrossQuestion
41	[46]	2022	CrossQuestion multiplayer game
42	[47]	2022	Moodle, Quiz
43	[48]	2022	Educaplay
44	[49]	2019	Moodle
45	[50]	2020	Ed Puzzle, LMS Moodle platform
46	[51]	2018	iSpring Learn, LMS
47	[52]	2022	Moodles
48	[53]	2022	Saudi national online learning
49	[54]	2022	Self-develop gamification learning
50	[55]	2022	Kahoot! And LearningApps
51	[56]	2022	Kahoot!
52	[57]	2019	Trivia quiz game

3.4. Game activity and game element

The teaching and learning process is delivered through GFC techniques, with varied activities based on the data gathered. Figure 6 depicts the proportion of classroom activities that utilize the GFC technique. According to the survey results, quizzes (41%) and learning activities (21%) were the areas where gamification was most prevalent. Meanwhile, the percentage for group projects (14%), formative assessment (11%), exercise (7%) and assessment (6%) accordingly.

Gamification contains various elements that might boost students' engagement and motivation in the classroom. According to the analysis done on the 52 articles, several gamification elements are applied. For example, according to the literature review, researchers preferred employing points and badges over other factors when rewarding winners. The gamification elements employed by the researchers in the GFC study are demonstrated in Figure 7.

Figure 6. Percentage of activities using gamification that was carried out

Figure 7. Game element use in GFC studies

3.5. Variables and impact on students' learning

Various variable was utilized in earlier investigations. However, most studies examined how gamification in FC impacted student performance, motivation, perception, and engagement. The variables examined alongside the GFC are listed in Table 5.

Table 5. Independent variables involved and their impact on the GFC study

No	Ref.	Variable	A gamified flipped classroom impact
1	[3]	Students' and teachers' perceptions	Gamified classroom benefits comprise improved learning performance and outcomes, developed learning abilities and confidence, as well as enhanced learning motivation and engagement, which both students and teachers acknowledged.
2	[5]	Intrinsic motivation, social relatedness, competence need satisfaction.	Gamified in-class activities have favorable benefits on intrinsic motivation as well as social connectedness. Nevertheless, they possess no discernible impact on meeting competence needs.
3	[6]	Student's engagement	With TechTeach, learning and enjoyment are possible in the classroom whether students are physically present.
4	[7]	Achievement and cognitive engagement	GFC enhanced students' cognitive engagement.
5	[10]	Students' motivation	The GFC strategy has a beneficial effect on students' motivation.
6	[11]	Study habits	The students liked the gamified CS1, team-based, flipped course and were inspired to enhance their study habits.
7	[12]	Student engagement, students' task orientation, students' satisfaction, students' attitude regarding the technique's complexity, students' general skills, students' knowledge, students' motivation, students' course learning outcomes.	Regarding technical difficulty, task orientation, student participation, satisfaction, knowledge, as well as learning motivation, the GFC learning technique performs better.
8	[13]	Students' achievement and perceptions	The use of digital game-based (DGB) as well as play curricular activity reflection discussion (PCARD) flipped learning considerably increases the grammar abilities of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learners over the control group.
9	[14]	Achievement (vocab)	Students may benefit from utilized the gamified flipped classroom application (GFCA) to enhance vocabulary proficiency.
10	[15]	Motivation	Students' motivation and competitiveness in class increased due to the gamification-enhanced activities that encouraged flipped learning.
11	[16]	Learner performance and need satisfaction	Because the GFC satisfies their intrinsic psychological requirements for competence, autonomy, and relatedness, participants have attained high motivation.
12	[17]	Students' motivation	When used effectively, gamification can encourage students and assist them in scaffolding reading assignments before lectures.
13	[18]	Students' motivation, perception	The goal-access-feedback-challenge-collaboration (GAFCC) style of gamification favors engaging learners because it provides students with the impression that the game benefits their learning.
14	[19]	Students' Perception	Applying gamification tactics also helped boost the program's favorable evaluation.
15	[20]	Students' perception	Over 60% of students agreed or strongly stated that GREENS helped enhance assessment, fun, learning, teamwork, as well as motivation.
16	[21]	Motivation and perception	The program received a very positive rating regarding motivation and sense of learning.
17	[22]	Attitudes, self-efficacy and emotions	Analysis of attitudes and self-efficacy reveals that most items exhibit higher self-efficacy and more favorable opinions following the intervention.
18	[23]	Student's perceived usefulness, engagement intention, and satisfaction	These strategies successfully alter students' perceived value and intended level of participation. From the participants' perspectives, gamification produces better results than an FC.
19	[24]	Students' perception and motivation	The findings presented increased student recognition and motivation with regard to effective teaching techniques, as well as a demonstrable enhancement in good feelings toward scientific topics and science education.
20	[25]	Students' engagement, effectiveness, the complexity of the GFC, student satisfaction, and task orientation	The GFC method has improved their experience for a better outcome. Additionally, it has aided their development as independent learners fiercely motivated to outperform their peers in class and on other GFC tasks.
21	[26]	Students' motivation	Based on the ARCS model, method, and tactics, students' motivation has been boosted and/or maintained by blended teaching methodologies (BTM), ultimately improving their learning.
22	[27]	Students' motivation, learning achievements and perception	Compared to the students participated in the control group, the experimental group's students exhibited a much higher motivation for academic performance.
23	[28]	Learning process	According to the statistics, the midterm tests, quizzes, lab work, average attendance, as well as final exams increased by almost 20% compared to the traditional classroom approach.
24	[29]	Student competencies	Compared to those who study the subject using conventional methods, the average grades in the evaluations significantly increased.
25	[30]	Students' behaviors, immersion experience, reading comprehension performance, as well as collaborative interaction relationship	This study addresses the need to encourage high-quality annotations in gamification methods, which can significantly improve students' reading comprehension.
26	[31]	Interaction data, students' participation, and achievement	The experimental group received greater involvement, achievement ratings, as well as interaction data than the control group.

Table 5. Independent variables involved and their impact on the GFC study (*continued*)

No	Ref.	Variable	A gamified flipped classroom impact
27	[32]	Curiosity and language anxiety	First, the two varieties mentioned earlier of epistemic curiosity negatively affect English learning anxiety. Second, deprivation-type epistemic curiosity (DEC) was positively correlated with attitude towards gamification (ATG), but interest-type epistemic curiosity (IEC) had no discernible effect on ATG. Third, ATG could accurately forecast how much students will learn.
28	[33]	Students' attitudes concerning competition, online collaboration, as well as learning gamification	The gamified learning experience positively impacted the attitudes of participants toward learning gamification.
29	[34]	Creative Thinking Skills	The research established no changes in the learning environment. Rather, the activity type as well as the interaction between teams, most significantly impacted critical thinking skills.
30	[35]	Students' learning in Chemistry	The experimental groups' learning activities and outcomes have attained classical completeness, according to the post- as well as pre-tests results.
31	[36]	Students' perception	In general, students possess positive opinions concerning the application as well as the added features. Other than that, 75% of students believe that the application can motivate students to stay participated in the physics course.
32	[37]	students' engagement	According to the findings of a semester-long study, there is no difference between poll- as well as point-based gamification. Nevertheless, point-based gamification in quiz mode increases reported student engagement more than in traditional lectures.
33	[38]	Learning performance, motivation, and meta-cognition tendency	Students from the gamified interactive e-book in the mathematical flipped classroom (GIEBFL) did much better than those from traditional instruction (TI) as well as conventional flipped learning (CFL). Other than that, the survey of students' motivation for learning revealed that GIEBFL students were more motivated than TI and CFL students. Here, GIEBFL students considerably outperformed TI students in terms of metacognition propensity.
34	[39]	Students' engagement and motivation	The various gamification tactics utilized to increase engagement received excellent feedback from students. In addition, students said they progressed in their writing, presentations, and comprehension throughout the course.
35	[40]	Students' achievement and satisfaction	A satisfying active learning environment is produced by constructing an empowered as well as co-creative gaming experience that supports students to establish value in general.
36	[41]	Vocabulary learning	The flipped context's use of gamification may substantially impact vocabulary development.
37	[42]	Students' perceptions	The students believed that using 'Kahoot!' boosted their knowledge of subjects, increased engagement, drove them to learn, and created a positive learning atmosphere.
38	[43]	Behavioral Engagement and Achievement	Students' involvement in the pre-class activities of the FC increased significantly while using the GFC mode of instruction compared to the control group.
39	[44]	Motivation, interest and fun	Happiness, pleasure, and enjoyment are three good emotions that dramatically rise following the intervention.
40	[45]	Student motivation	Gamification can increase student motivation and engagement in beneficial ways. In addition, it can improve students' grades.
41	[46]	Students' motivation	Learning effectiveness and learning motivating elements are significantly correlated. The game has a great effect on the motivation of the students as well.
42	[47]	Students' achievement and engagement	Traditional classes that have been gamified encourage student accomplishment, and FC that has been gamified encourage student engagement.
43	[48]	English oral communication ability	The students' oral communication skills in English could be enhanced by integrating task-based language training, flipped learning, as well as game-based learning.
44	[49]	Student engagement	Students in the gamification-enhanced flipped learning group performed the post- as well as pre-class tasks more frequently, produced artefacts of higher quality, and achieved considerably greater post-course test scores compared to their non-gamified counterparts.
45	[50]	Motivation, autonomy and self-regulation	When these techniques were utilized, students' motivation, autonomy, and self-control increased as they interacted with the subject's material.
46	[51]	Students' learning performance and perceived motivation	The students' perception of competence, autonomy, and relatedness was positive. They also performed better and achieved high exam scores.
47	[52]	Student skills competency and learning motivation.	Gamified flipped classrooms enhance students' self-confidence, skills knowledge, intensity of preparation, as well as motivation, in comparison to the traditional flipped classrooms.
48	[53]	Student achievement, motivations, and satisfaction	An e-learning gamification increases students' motivation and satisfaction in computer science online courses but has no effect on their achievement.
49	[54]	Student engagement and satisfaction	Comparing a conventional flipped classroom, the escape box format is well-liked by students. It presents enhanced ratings in appropriate levels with regard to effective learning materials as well as complexity.
50	[55]	Student achievement	Students in gamification and flipped learning methods are more successful compared to students in the traditional method.
51	[56]	Student engagement	Students scored better in gamified quizzes when they prepared in advance in flipped learning sessions.
52	[57]	Students 'motivation	High levels of student motivation, increased class participation, and improved subject achievements (marks).

4. DISCUSSION

This systematic analysis's findings are concentrated on studies that examine the impact of gamification strategies and flipped classrooms on education. Other than that, this study fills the gaps in the research mentioned earlier and provides valuable suggestions and recommendations for future studies on gamified flipped classrooms. Apart from that, SDT [5], [17]–[19], [22], [32], [34], [39], [40], [44], [48], [50]–[55] became the basis of the majority of gamified flipped classrooms study.

However, most articles fail to clarify how the study's underlying theory and the real gamification activities relate. For example, 21 of the 52 articles do not mention any theory or model employed to implement their research. In addition, most scholars applied the Attention, Relevance, Confidence and Satisfaction model to examine how GFC impacted students' motivation [10], [26], [33], [45], [46].

Consequently, most researchers conducted investigations utilizing experimental quasi-studies as their primary methodology Figure 5. Both treatment and control groups of students were established, having the treatment group undergoing interventions. Students will take pre-test exams before learning about GFC. Consequently, after the intervention, a post-test exam will be conducted to observe how successful the interventions were. In addition to experiments, the mixed-method study included information gathered through monitoring, interviews, and open-ended surveys. In comparison, different study [33] employed a qualitative research approach.

As a result, the systematic review analysis's findings revealed a variety of online tools and platforms that researchers utilized to examine the efficiency and influence of GFC on student learning. Besides that, the researchers are more enthusiastic about utilizing the Socrative, Kahoot!, and Moodle learning management systems. In addition, several academicians have developed unique and inventive gamification programs to conduct their GFC investigations. One is Triviachis, a hybrid of the Spanish board game Parchis and the trivia quiz game [57]. To determine the effectiveness of gamified questions in English grammar, [32] created the TipOn quiz, an artificial intelligence (AI)-enabled, web-based online learning tool to examine students' physics perceptions [36]. Note that gamification activities encourage activity completion, improve learning, and address issues [58]. Quizzes, formative assessments [3], [26], [31], [42], [46], learning activities, in-class instruction and assessment, as well as group projects [12], [34] were some of the gamification techniques employed in the researchers' study.

We established that the most often utilized game mechanics in GFC in education were points, badges, feedback, levels, and leaderboards. This aligns with previous research [12], who opined that the most frequently utilized game mechanics are levels, badges, trophies, achievements, competitions, and point systems. According to our study's findings, most research articles reveal favorable attitudes and learning outcomes, which is consistent with other studies findings.

Consequently, this review offers a thorough assessment of the relevant empirical evidence. Gamified flipped classrooms generally produce favorable academic outcomes. Apart from that, the majority of the research that were evaluated stated that gamification encourages enhancements in student achievement [5], [7], [13], [14], [27], [40], [43], [47], [53], [55], motivation [5], [10], [13], [16], [18], [19], [22], [23], [25], [27], [28], [39], [40], [46], [51]–[53], and engagement [6], [7], [57], [13], [24], [26], [38], [40], [44], [48], [56]. Furthermore, numerous studies have already established the effectiveness of gamified flipped classrooms over conventional teaching and learning.

5. CONCLUSION

Gamification uses game-based components or mechanics to boost motivation and interest through competition, such as leaderboards, leader scores, points and badges. Besides that, gamification components can encourage students to set more focused objectives, be more persistent, learn by repetition through teamwork, and engage in enjoyable competition with their peers. Moreover, gamification also encourages competitiveness and maintains student motivation in the classroom for longer. Students who use the gamification strategy to learn become more confident, active, and involved in classroom activities. Other than that, they develop better problem-solving, communication, and thinking skills. Gamification is thought to enhance fundamental knowledge while also raising student achievement. Additionally, gamification fosters collaborative learning, student-centered learning, and positive learning possibilities while providing an opportunity to incorporate students' thoughts, feelings, and behaviors. It is proven that instructors can transform classrooms into pleasant environments. By incorporating gamification elements such as giving assessments, applying gamification rules, time constraints, and accuracy, they can encourage action, motivate the students and gain positive feedback.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. C. Piñero Charlo *et al.*, "Preface for the special issue 'trends in educational gamification: Challenges and learning opportunities'," *Education Sciences*, vol. 12, no. 3, p. 179, Mar. 2022, doi: 10.3390/educsci12030179.
- [2] M. Kalogiannakis, S. Papadakis, and A.-I. Zourmpakis, "Gamification in Science Education. A Systematic Review of the Literature," *Education Sciences*, vol. 11, no. 1, p. 22, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.3390/educsci11010022.
- [3] D. Zou, "Gamified flipped EFL classroom for primary education: Student and teacher perceptions," *Journal of Computers in Education*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 213–228, Jun. 2020, doi: 10.1007/s40692-020-00153-w.
- [4] J. Bergmann and A. Sams, *Flip your classroom: reach every student in every class every day*. International Society for Technology in Education, 2012.
- [5] M. Sailer and M. Sailer, "Gamification of in-class activities in flipped classroom lectures," *British Journal of Educational Technology*, vol. 52, no. 1, pp. 75–90, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.1111/bjet.12948.
- [6] F. Portela, "TechTeach—an innovative method to increase the students engagement at classrooms," *Information*, vol. 11, no. 10, Oct. 2020, doi: 10.3390/info11100483.
- [7] C. K. Lo and K. F. Hew, "A comparison of flipped learning with gamification, traditional learning, and online independent study: The effects on students' mathematics achievement and cognitive engagement," *Interactive Learning Environments*, vol. 28, no. 4, pp. 464–481, May 2020, doi: 10.1080/10494820.2018.1541910.
- [8] S. Bai, K. F. Hew, and B. Huang, "Does gamification improve student learning outcome? Evidence from a meta-analysis and synthesis of qualitative data in educational contexts," *Educational Research Review*, vol. 30, Jun. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.edurev.2020.100322.
- [9] D. Moher, "Preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses: the PRISMA statement," *Annals of Internal Medicine*, vol. 151, no. 4, pp. 264–269, Aug. 2009, doi: 10.7326/0003-4819-151-4-200908180-00135.
- [10] S. Azia, I. Abu Bakar, and A. Ashardi, "The effectiveness of the use gamified flipped classroom approach towards student's motivation at pre-university level," in *Proceedings of International Conference on The Future of Education (IConFed)*, 2020, pp. 17–18.
- [11] G. Sprint and E. Fox, "Improving student study choices in cs1 with gamification and flipped classrooms," *Annual Conference on Innovation and Technology in Computer Science Education, ITiCSE*, 2020, pp. 773–779, doi: 10.1145/3328778.3366888.
- [12] U. K. Durrani, G. Al Naymat, R. M. Ayoubi, M. M. Kamal, and H. Hussain, "Gamified flipped classroom versus traditional classroom learning: Which approach is more efficient in business education?" *The International Journal of Management Education*, vol. 20, no. 1, Mar. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.ijme.2021.100595.
- [13] H. S. Rad, "Effect of PCaRD DGB flipped learning on EFL learners' grammar Skill," *The Journal of Asia TEFL*, vol. 18, no. 2, pp. 544–558, Jun. 2021, doi: 10.18823/asiatefl.2021.18.2.10.544.
- [14] V. Botmart, "The effects of gamified flipped classroom application on learning English vocabulary for Thai University students in EFL context," Master Thesis, Suranaree University of Technology, 2019.
- [15] H. H. Ā-zer, S. Kanbul, and F. Ozdamli, "Effects of the gamification supported flipped classroom model on the attitudes and opinions regarding game-coding education," *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (iJET)*, vol. 13, no. 01, Jan. 2018, doi: 10.3991/ijet.v13i01.7634.
- [16] Z. Zainuddin, M. Shujahat, S. K. W. Chu, H. Haruna, and R. Farida, "The effects of gamified flipped instruction on learner performance and need satisfaction: A study in a low-tech setting," *Information and Learning Sciences*, vol. 120, no. 11/12, pp. 789–802, Nov. 2019, doi: 10.1108/ILS-07-2019-0067.
- [17] L. Tan, "Meaningful gamification and students' motivation: A strategy for scaffolding reading material," *Online Learning*, vol. 22, no. 2, pp. 141–156, Jun. 2018, doi: 10.24059/olj.v22i2.1167.
- [18] B. Huang and K. F. Hew, "Implementing a theory-driven gamification model in higher education flipped courses: Effects on out-of-class activity completion and quality of artifacts," *Computers & Education*, vol. 125, pp. 254–272, Oct. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.compedu.2018.06.018.
- [19] C. J. Gómez-Carrasco, J. Monteagudo-Fernández, J. R. Moreno-Vera, and M. Sainz-Gómez, "Evaluation of a gamification and flipped-classroom program used in teacher training: Perception of learning and outcome," *PLOS ONE*, vol. 15, no. 7, p. e0236083, Jul. 2020, doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0236083.
- [20] D. Jiménez-Rodríguez, T. Belmonte Garcia, and V. Arizo Luque, "Perception of nursing students about the implementation of GREENS© methodology in nursing studies," *Nurse Education Today*, vol. 92, Sep. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.nedt.2020.104495.
- [21] C.-J. Gómez-Carrasco, J. Monteagudo-Fernández, J.-R. Moreno-Vera, and M. Sainz-Gómez, "Effects of a gamification and flipped-classroom program for teachers in training on motivation and learning perception," *Education Sciences*, vol. 9, no. 4, p. 299, Dec. 2019, doi: 10.3390/educsci9040299.
- [22] F. Yllana-Prieto, J. S. Jeong, and D. González-Gómez, "An online-based edu-escape room: A comparison study of a multidimensional domain of PSTs with flipped sustainability-STEM contents," *Sustainability*, vol. 13, no. 3, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.3390/su13031032.
- [23] M. Thongmak, "The student experience of student-centered learning methods: Comparing gamification and flipped classroom," *Education for Information*, vol. 35, no. 2, pp. 99–127, Jun. 2019, doi: 10.3233/EFI-180189.
- [24] F. Zamora-Polo, M. Corrales-Serrano, J. Sánchez-Martín, and L. Espejo-Antúnez, "Nonscientific university students training in general science using an active-learning merged pedagogy: Gamification in a flipped classroom," *Education Sciences*, vol. 9, no. 4, Dec. 2019, doi: 10.3390/educsci9040297.
- [25] U. Durrani, "Gamified flipped classroom learning approach: A case study of AJ University," in *2019 IEEE International Conference on Engineering, Technology and Education (TALE)*, 2019, no. 1, pp. 1–5, doi: 10.1109/TALE48000.2019.9225919.
- [26] U. K. Durrani and M. M. Kamal, "Application of ARCS model for a blended teaching methodologies: A study of students' motivation amid the COVID-19," *EAI Endorsed Transactions on e-Learning*, vol. 7, no. 21, p. 168721, Jul. 2018, doi: 10.4108/eai.17-2-2021.168721.
- [27] G. Aşıksoy, "The effects of the gamified flipped classroom environment (GFCE) on students' motivation, learning achievements and perception in a physics course," *Quality & Quantity*, vol. 52, no. S1, pp. 129–145, 2018, doi: 10.1007/s11135-017-0597-1.
- [28] A. Zhamanov, Seong-MooYoo, Z. Sakhiyeva, and M. Zhaparov, "Implementation and evaluation of flipped classroom as IoT element into learning process of computer network education," *International Journal of Information and Communication Technology Education*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 30–47, Apr. 2018, doi: 10.4018/IJICTE.2018040103.
- [29] E. Toriz, "Learning based on flipped classroom with just-in-time teaching, Unity3D, gamification and educational spaces," *International Journal on Interactive Design and Manufacturing (IJIDeM)*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 1159–1173, Sep. 2019, doi: 10.1007/s12008-019-00560-z.

- [30] C.-M. Chen, M.-C. Li, and T.-C. Chen, "A web-based collaborative reading annotation system with gamification mechanisms to improve reading performance," *Computers & Education*, vol. 144, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.compedu.2019.103697.
- [31] A. Y. Gündüz and B. Akkoyunlu, "Effectiveness of gamification in flipped learning," *SAGE Open*, vol. 10, no. 4, Oct. 2020, doi: 10.1177/2158244020979837.
- [32] J.-C. Hong, M.-Y. Hwang, Y.-H. Liu, and K.-H. Tai, "Effects of gamifying questions on English grammar learning mediated by epistemic curiosity and language anxiety," *Computer Assisted Language Learning*, vol. 35, no. 7, pp. 1458–1482, Sep. 2022, doi: 10.1080/09588221.2020.1803361.
- [33] Y. An, "A qualitative investigation of team-based gamified learning in an online environment," *Educational Process International Journal*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 73–91, 2021, doi: 10.22521/edupij.2021.104.5.
- [34] J. Forte-Celaya, L. Ibarra, and L. D. Glasserman-Morales, "Analysis of creative thinking skills development under active learning strategies," *Education Sciences*, vol. 11, no. 10, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.3390/educsci1100621.
- [35] A. Lutfi, Suyono, and R. Hidayah, "Applying gamification to improve the quality of teaching and learning of chemistry in high schools: A case study of Indonesia," *Asia-Pacific Forum on Science Learning and Teaching*, vol. 20, no. 2, pp. 1–17, 2021.
- [36] D. Y. Tan and C. W. Cheah, "Developing a gamified AI-enabled online learning application to improve students' perception of university physics," *Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 2, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.caeai.2021.100032.
- [37] S. E. Koppitsch and J. Meyer, "Do points matter? the effects of gamification activities with and without points on student learning and engagement," *Marketing Education Review*, vol. 32, no. 1, pp. 45–53, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.1080/10528008.2021.1887745.
- [38] J. Zhao, G.-J. Hwang, S.-C. Chang, Q. Yang, and A. Nokkaew, "Effects of gamified interactive e-books on students' flipped learning performance, motivation, and meta-cognition tendency in a mathematics course," *Educational Technology Research and Development*, vol. 69, no. 6, pp. 3255–3280, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.1007/s11423-021-10053-0.
- [39] J. Hammill, T. Nguyen, and F. Henderson, "Encouraging the flip with a gamified process," *International Journal of Educational Research Open*, vol. 2, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.ijedro.2021.100085.
- [40] L. R. Murrillo-Zamorano, J. Á. López Sánchez, A. L. Godoy-Caballero, and C. Bueno Muñoz, "Gamification and active learning in higher education: is it possible to match digital society, academia and students' interests?" *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, vol. 18, no. 1, p. 15, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.1186/s41239-021-00249-y.
- [41] F. Fahandezh and A. Mohammadi, "The effect of gamified flipped classroom on the improvement of vocabulary learning of Iranian pre-intermediate EFL learners," *Vision: Journal for Language and Foreign Language Learning*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 83–98, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.21580/vjv10i28577.
- [42] C. G. Ruiz, "The effect of integrating Kahoot! and peer instruction in the Spanish flipped classroom: The student perspective," *Journal of Spanish Language Teaching*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 63–78, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.1080/23247797.2021.1913832.
- [43] G. Asiksoy and S. Canbolat, "The effects of the gamified flipped classroom method on petroleum engineering students' pre-class online behavioural engagement and achievement," *International Journal of Engineering Pedagogy (iJEP)*, vol. 11, no. 5, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.3991/ijep.v11i5.21957.
- [44] F. Yllana Prieto, J. S. Jeong, and D. González-Gómez, "Virtual escape room and STEM content: Effects on the affective domain on teacher trainees," *Journal of Technology and Science Education*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 331–342, May 2021, doi: 10.3926/jotse.1163.
- [45] U. Durrani, R. Alnajjar, A. Al Muaitah, A. Daqaq, A. Salah, and R. Zeyad, "CrossQuestion game: A design of a group-based assessment tool to enhance student motivation during pandemic," *International Journal of Information and Education Technology*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 15–20, 2022, doi: 10.18178/ijiet.2022.12.1.1581.
- [46] U. Durrani, O. Hujran, and A. S. Al-Adwan, "CrossQuestion game: A group-based assessment for gamified flipped classroom experience using the ARCS model," *Contemporary Educational Technology*, vol. 14, no. 2, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.30935/cedtech/11568.
- [47] L.-K. Ng and C.-K. Lo, "Flipped classroom and gamification approach: Its impact on performance and academic commitment on sustainable learning in education," *Sustainability*, vol. 14, no. 9, Apr. 2022, doi: 10.3390/su14095428.
- [48] K. Muntrikaeo and K. Poonpon, "The effects of task-based instruction using online language games in a flipped learning environment (TGF) on English oral communication ability of Thai secondary students," *English Language Teaching*, vol. 15, no. 3, p. 9, Feb. 2022, doi: 10.5539/elt.v15n3p9.
- [49] B. Huang, K. F. Hew, and C. K. Lo, "Investigating the effects of gamification-enhanced flipped learning on undergraduate students' behavioral and cognitive engagement," *Interactive Learning Environments*, vol. 27, no. 8, pp. 1106–1126, Nov. 2019, doi: 10.1080/10494820.2018.1495653.
- [50] G. Gómez-García, J. A. Marín-Marín, J.-M. Romero-Rodríguez, M. Ramos Navas-Parejo, and C. Rodríguez Jiménez, "Effect of the flipped classroom and gamification methods in the development of a didactic unit on healthy habits and diet in primary education," *Nutrients*, vol. 12, no. 8, p. 2210, Jul. 2020, doi: 10.3390/nu12082210.
- [51] Z. Zainuddin, "Students' learning performance and perceived motivation in gamified flipped-class instruction," *Computers & Education*, vol. 126, pp. 75–88, Nov. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.compedu.2018.07.003.
- [52] M. E. H. Elzaky, H. M. M. Elhabashy, W. G. M. Ali, and S. M. E. Allam, "Effect of gamified flipped classroom on improving nursing students' skills competency and learning motivation: A randomized controlled trial," *BMC Nursing*, vol. 21, no. 1, p. 316, Nov. 2022, doi: 10.1186/s12912-022-01096-6.
- [53] E. Alsadoon, A. Alkhwajah, and A. Bin Suhaim, "Effects of a gamified learning environment on students' achievement, motivations, and satisfaction," *Heliyon*, vol. 8, no. 8, Aug. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e10249.
- [54] C. Cantwell, S. Saadat, S. Sakaria, W. Wiechmann, and G. Sudario, "Escape box and puzzle design as educational methods for engagement and satisfaction of medical student learners in emergency medicine: Survey study," *BMC Medical Education*, vol. 22, no. 1, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.1186/s12909-022-03585-3.
- [55] G. Tarhan and G. Öztürk, "Flipped learning and gamification in information technologies and software course," *International Journal of Contemporary Educational Research*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 62–77, 2022, doi: 10.33200/ijcer.969959.
- [56] C. Anane, "Gamified flipped learning in a French foreign language class: Efficiency and student perception," *Frontiers in Education*, vol. 7, no. 2013, 2022, doi: 10.3389/educ.2022.994892.
- [57] M. Rodríguez, I. Díaz, E. J. Gonzalez, and M. González-Miquel, "Reprint of: Motivational active learning: An integrated approach to teaching and learning process control," *Education for Chemical Engineers*, vol. 26, pp. 8–13, Jan. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.ece.2019.01.002.
- [58] K. M. Kapp, *The gamification of learning and instruction game-based method and strategies for training and education*, 1st ed. Pfeiffer, 2012.

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